

QUIZ**LAST NAME: THAKKAR****FIRST NAME: KARISHMA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

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QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the first step in researching an essay topic?

- Research topic by using credible academic sources.
- Analyze the question and define key terms.¹**
- Complete or check references.
- Take notes from preliminary reading.

2. What are the main structures of an essay?

- Body and hypothesis.
- Thesis, body, and hypothesis.

¹Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition*. (Bangui: Euclid University), 8.

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Introduction, body, and conclusion. ²

Research, hypothesis, Conclusion.

3. What is capitalized?

Common nouns.

Groups of Institutions.

Page.

Proper Nouns. ³

4. What are four parts of a initial draft of a dissertation?

Concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript. ⁴

Statement of problem, research questions, data analysis, and manuscript.

Hypothesis, manuscript, first draft, and title page.

Social significance of problem, figures, title page, and research questions.

5. What are three successful research factors?

Visualizing success, writing a hypothesis, and editing.

Formulating research questions, picking a topic, and critical review of literature.

Good planning, analyzing data, and creating research outline.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, [12](#).

³ Daniel Alexander et al., *European Commission English Style Guide*, Eighth Edition (European Commission, 2021), 23.

⁴ James P. Sampson 2017. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition, (Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

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Good communication, good planning, and effective process for writing.⁵

6. What is a schema?

- A initial hypothesis which needs further questioning.
- An abstract structure of information which helps in organizing, remembering, and using information.**⁶
- A section in a dissertation that comes after literature review.
- Data Analysis and Tables inserted to further prove a hypothesis.

7. What is a statement of problem?

- Succinct statement of dilemma research questions are intended to resolve.**⁷
- First step in formulating a hypothesis.
- A review of chapter that is part of the dissertation introduction chapter.
- A balance of literature that highlights a theory.

8. What is an element of initial research?

- Formulate a initial hypothesis.
- Plan out your initial dissertation project.
- Build a storyboard and guide your work.

⁵ Ibid., 13.

⁶ Ibid., 16.

⁷ Ibid., 28.

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Ask a question worth answering.⁸

9. There are three types of sources: primary, secondary, and tertiary. What are tertiary sources used for?

Get a broad overview of your topic.⁹

Make a scholarly argument.

Original materials filled with raw data.

Keep up with the work of other scholars.

10. Once a working hypothesis becomes a claim or assertion, what is one way you go about further supporting it?

Formulate new questions to create another hypothesis.

Make new claims based on tertiary sources.

Keep backing it up with reasons and evidence.¹⁰

Never use warrants to guide further research.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press), 10.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 26.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 53.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.